

Software Bill of Materials

Used Software

- Rstudio for creating R scripts and running them. Version: R 4.3.3
- Pycharm Python-IDE for creating the makefile in the programming language Python. Version: pycharm 2025.2.3. Used and imported Pycharm modules for the main program: import requests, import csv, import webbrowser as wb (for viewing PDF with makefile)
- TinyTex, installed via Rstudio to generate PDF from Rmarkdown file.
- TeXLive. Version: pdfTeX 3.141592653-2.6-1.40.28 (TeX Live 2025)

Produced Data (on the basis of the research paper)

- One CSV Data table (called Dataset_x_y_Pairs) with x and y values (taken from the original research paper)
- One R project (called statistical_values) for visualizing the data in the table (originally published in the paper) → R script (called script_readtable) → Rmarkdown (found in the Rstudio Project and in Makefile) with the main theses of the paper, knittable within Rstudio) → PNG file of the visualized figures, created and then exported from Rstudio
- One Rmarkdown file (the same as above) as HTML and as PDF
- One Makefile with which the Rmarkdown and PDF can be viewed alongside the x and y values and visualization